

MODELING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATIONAL-INTELLECTUAL SKILLS OF FUTURE ENGINEERS

Absamatov Zukhriddin Akhmad Ugli

**Karshi Engineering - Economics Institute, Senior Lecturer of the Department of Higher
Mathematics.**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8394379>

Annotation: Maskur in the article on modeling in the development of informative-intellectual skills, the formation and development of professional skills of Engineers, the development of methodology for applying new technologies, the use of modeling programs, the training of Engineers in programs, on how engineers create a mathematical model, on online video courses, analysis of modern modeling methodologies, 3D modeling has been highlighted, as well as its own models in the use of modeling programs in the teaching of Information Technology in technical systems.

Keywords: competency approach, informational and pedagogical technology, technological processes, modeling, 3D-modeling, "MATLAB" program, design, computer engineering, virtual experience.

Introduction. Implementation of a competent approach, conducting active and interactive (computer simulators, businessmen's game, consideration of specific situations, project method, etc.) forms in the organization of educational process training, formation of professional skills of engineers and for the purpose of development, together with work outside the auditorium, modern informational and pedagogical technologies used in world pedagogical practice, effective teaching strategies, modern information technologies, methods and methods should be widely used.

Purchase of modern computer equipment, software for it, as well as development of methods of applying new technologies are activities that require significant investment of time and money. It will be possible to fully assess the effectiveness of these investments in terms of improving the quality of education only after conducting all stages of pedagogical experience. At the initial stage, it is necessary to perform a preliminary assessment of the possibility of increasing efficiency due to the use of computer models in the study of technological processes.

Contrasted with the synthesis method prevalent in higher education teaching practice is the research method, which is based on the premise that scientific ideas can only be fully understood in the context of their emergence and subsequent research. . In the literature, it is called "BSCS model" or "Dj. "Schwab model" (named after the author - an American pedagogue) is found [1]. The method is carried out in the form of "invention proposal" or "research proposal", which does not organize and direct the search, but implies the proposal of the search based on initial ideas and assumptions that change as knowledge develops. Each of the "suggestions" introduces students not to evidence and knowledge, but to the process of seeking knowledge and engages students in this process.

According to A.N. Leontev, the activity of internal thinking not only determines the external, practical activity, but also has the same structure [2]. Internal, theoretical activity may include external, practical actions, and these external actions may, in turn, include separate internal, mental logical or mathematical operations. The more practical activity is intellectualized, the more clearly the integration of mental and practical processes is observed, and on the other

hand, the same situation is observed when mental activity is armed with external technical means.

Yu.V. Sachkov, speaking about the technical means of learning activities, considers it a mistake that the role of experience is only to confirm or deny theoretical foundations and conclusions. This interpretation leads to the loss of the main meaning of the experiential beginning of learning. "Tools are special "expanders", "continuator", "supplements" of the senses of human organs. Accordingly, the main "task" of experience is to provide a more and more sensitive emotional analysis of existence" [3]. Modern experience has an independent value, even if it does not have the possibility of a serious theoretical foundation. This independent value of experience is expressed in the fact that it is not just a thinking person, but a "material-object moving" person who realizes the essence.

For engineers in the field of new knowledge, their learning activity will depend on the teacher's ability to awaken and support that activity. The ability to occupy an audience is formed on the basis of the teacher's ability to lead his students through a thin border between known and unknown. Deepening to one side or another-the audience's interest disappears [4].

An unacceptable stop in the field of certain things can be observed when solving tasks in practical training. When solving a system of linear equations, the technology of calculating the determinant can be of interest only from the point of view of Mathematics, while programming requires a tool that immediately performs these calculations. Increasing the complexity, and from this, the importance of technological processes, the attention of Engineers is not distributed in favor of the main subject of training. Performing a calculation using a calculator is a measure from desperation, and at the time of calculations, one has to endure a loss of interest in the science of programming. In the artificial retention of science when attention decreases, we observe that the learning activities of intelligent and demanding engineers decrease, and its exchange with the activities of the teacher at the same time at the will of the teacher. By helping to capture practical training dynamics by using a computer math package, such as "MATLAB", it requires only three actions to solve a system of equations. Only 10-15 years ago, the proposal to create a simulator for engineers studying technological processes seemed unusual.

In addition to the function of training engineers, the computer allows the teacher to request a printout of the results of his preparation for the laboratory exercise, without burdening the engineers with additional paperwork. It is precisely the lack of control over initial preparation for laboratory training that allows engineers to ignore this preparation. The traditional solution to the problem is to conduct a colloquium, based on the results of which the student is allowed to do the work or not. However, lack of audience time often prevents this method from being used.

The introduction of computer modeling into the teaching process, in our opinion, helps to implement the principle of visualization. The authors of "Visual School" put the principle of visuality on the basis of "constructing special information environments adapted for the effective functioning of visual thinking" [5]. In this, visual thinking is considered as a special type of brain activity, "its product is the creation of new images, which carry a certain meaning load and make the value visible, and create new visual forms" [6].

The development of didactic materials on the study of technological processes in accordance with the methodological foundations developed by the “visual school” can be one of the stages of deepening the methodology for using computer modeling. At the initial stage of the creation of this methodology, we note that computer graphics and animation significantly expand the arsenal of tools used to create an information environment of teaching. They allow you to create a new class of visual guides – interactive objects.

However, we will focus on the positive role of computer technology in overcoming the shortcomings of systemicity and continuity. In the implementation of the basic pedagogical principles, it is necessary to carefully substantiate the idea of negative consequences.

An intelligent, creative, meticulous individual applies his intelligence and creativity in a work that he understands and agrees to do. The need to systematize the collected experimental and theoretical material arises to the researcher of the surrounding world so that when working with a large volume of evidence there is no possibility without qualitative generalization of them. The work of the creator of the physical phenomena models of the classifier in this case will be interesting and rich in creativity.

The virtual experience should not lag far behind the real experience in terms of dynamics: if the lecture material is not just written to the audience, but understood by them, then engineers participate in the creation of a mathematical model and its tests. They will be able to see the prospects of application of their knowledge, make conclusions about the areas of application of theoretical programming calculation methods. In this, we can see the implementation of the scientific principle of teaching.

Traditionally, any engineering curriculum in universities includes graphic design subjects, where engineers spend at least one academic year receiving basic training in presentation systems, drafting, technical illustration, and ALT.

First, the engineers had to memorize or annotate the presented modeling procedures and could only do them after the lesson. The amount of new information after an hour lecture would be overwhelming for engineers. Small practical steps that are important to the learning process were not available.

Second, the lectures showed a lack of interaction. Engineers cannot follow the instructions given at the same time, so they cannot face problems (in the modeling process) that can become the subject of discussion.

Thirdly, during the training, the engineers were noticeably bored by the fact that they were in a passive role. Boredom is a common problem in the educational process.

After making the decision to implement this style, video lessons relevant to the course will be recorded. Video lessons are posted on YouTube for free. In addition, channels and groups have been created in messengers (WhatsApp, Viber and Telegram) and social networks, which engineers use a lot today. In these channels and groups, educational materials (video lessons, presentations, tutorials, tasks and announcements) were placed. After that, there were changes in the organization of the training process, and at the same time, it provided significant improvements in the results of Engineers.

Those that are the main reasons why we decided to implement a new approach were considered:

- Engineers participated in the training without any initial knowledge. It took a long time to explain the basics of the three-dimensional modeling process;

- uring lectures, engineers were passive and bored. This has become a major obstacle to the learning process;
- there was no interaction between the teacher and the student necessary for a successful learning process in the lectures;
- many of the tasks specified during the lectures were in many cases required to be repeated later during practical training;
- due to slow development, engineers were quickly losing interest in science.

Our main task was to bring the basics of the three-dimensional modeling process beyond the classroom. Also encourage engineers to do their basic training before arriving in class; provide base knowledge to engineers 24 hours a day, anywhere the internet is available; help engineers prepare for discussions during training; interest them in science and awaken a competitive spirit in them; to provide them with the most optimal teaching methodology (nowadays young people receive the necessary information from video cameras and the internet).

These online classes and video lessons explain each part of the science program step by step. Each study week has a corresponding set of textbooks, which must be approved before training. They are made for beginners. No preliminary knowledge is required.

The first significant improvement in the educational process was the preparation for the lectures of Engineers.

They were familiar with terminology and 3D modeling, work environment and basic commands. This turned the lecture into a completely new concept. Instead of spending time learning the basics, dynamic discussions began almost every time the lesson began. Engineers gave their advanced solutions to the problems presented in the textbooks. They soon began a cross-competition to explain different approaches to modeling specific elements.

These competitions were excellent for the training process, so we created several quizzes to determine some of the rules of the competition and apply prizes that affect the final grades of active engineers.

Excellent changes were made in the training, which no one expected. From classrooms filled with engineers who are bored and complain about everything, we came to engineers where students do not get out of training after the end of the lesson. They began to enjoy acquiring new skills and knowledge.

Thus, much better cooperation was achieved between professors and engineers, with an increased interest in mastering non-trivial materials. At the end of each semester, engineers can anonymously comment on the course and evaluate their teachers.

In conclusion, it is necessary to develop a specific model or improve existing models when using modeling programs in the teaching of natural-scientific disciplines in higher educational institutions of the technical direction. It is the basis for the study of natural-scientific Sciences for students of the information and communication systems direction of technological process management or the undergraduate direction related to automation. From this point of view, it will be advisable to teach the use of this section as a tool for solving practical tasks related to modeling in a deeper and more practical study in programming, modeling courses.

References:

1. Курбанов Ш., Сейтхалилов Э. Управление качеством образования. Монография. – Ташкент: Шарк, 2004. – 705 с.
2. Лаптев В.В. Важные проблемы компьютерного обучения в современной школе. // Проблемы совершенствования физического образования. С.-Пб., Издательство РГПУ им. Герцена, 1998. - 188с.
3. Сачков Ю. В. Научный метод и его структура // Вопросы философии. 1983.-№2.
4. Рубинштейн С. Л. О природе мышления и его составе. // Хрестоматия по общей психологии. Психология мышления. - М., 1981.
5. Роберт И.В. Основные направления научных исследований в области информатизации профессионального образования / И.В. Роберт, В.А. Поляков. – М.: Образование и информатика, 2004. – 96 с.
6. Shadiev, R., Khimmataliev, D., Fayzullaev, R., & Chorshanbiev, Z. (2020). Professional culture of the future teacher of vocational education: a communicative aspect. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(4), 399-400.
7. Джемс У. Мышление. // Хрестоматия по общей психологии. Психология мышления. - М., 1981. - 367с.
8. Ибрагимов У.М. "Внедрение методологии перевернутый класс в технические вузы в предмет по моделированию". //Материалы III международная научно-практическая конференция «Наука и образование в современном мире: вызовы XXI века // Нур-Султан. //2019. С 43-47.
9. Esanpulatovich, Z. C. (2021). BASES OF USING PROJECT TECHNOLOGY IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIFFERENTIATION OF EDUCATION. *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities*, 1(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).
10. Chorshanbiyev, Z. E. (2019). The pedagogical potential of e-learning environments to improve mathematical and scientific training of engineering personnel. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(1).
11. Gayratovich, Ergashev Nuriddin. "A MODEL OF THE STRUCTURAL STRUCTURE OF PEDAGOGICAL STRUCTURING OF EDUCATION IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES." *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research* 13 (2023): 64-69.
12. G'ayratovich, Ergashev Nuriddin. "The Theory of the Use of Cloud Technologies in the Implementation of Hierarchical Preparation of Engineers." *Eurasian Research Bulletin* 7 (2022): 18-21.
13. Ergashev, N. "Theory of training of pedagogical personnel in higher education using cloud technologies in the conditions of digital education." *International Conference on Problems of Improving Education and Science*. Vol. 1. No. 02. 2022.